

Synthesis, structural interpretation, biological activity and DNA cleavage studies of Cu^{II} ternary complexes of 3-acyl 2-(2'-hydroxy-5-substituted phenyl)benzothiazolines and L-glycine

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Abstract : The formation of 3-acyl 2-(2'-hydroxy-5-Y phenyl)benzothiazoline (Y = H, Cl, NO₂, OCH₃) ternary Cu^{II} complexes and their characterization by various spectro-analytical techniques have been studied in the present investigation. The spectro-analytical data from elemental analyses, magnetic moments, molar conductance, electronic, mass, TG, IR spectral measurement and room temperature ESR spectra of complexes inferred the electronic and geometric properties of metal complexes. Antibacterial and antifungal activity against *E. coli*, *S. marcescens*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis* and *C. albicans* was assayed by the agar disk diffusion method for the title compounds and their corresponding Cu^{II} ternary complexes. DNA cleavage studies performed on the title compounds and their Cu^{II} ternary complexes showed that Cu^{II}-AHCPBT-Gly and Cu^{II}-AHNPBT-Gly cleaved the PBR322 DNA, wherein the super coiled DNA (form I) is converted into relaxed DNA (form II).

Keywords : Benzothiazoline, Cu^{II} ternary complexes, DNA cleavage studies, ESR studies.

Introduction

The metal complexes of transition elements with heterocyclic ligands especially those containing nitrogen and sulphur have diverse application in various fields including biology. Metal complexes with benzothiazolines have gained and attained special interest in the recent years due to their biological importance. Perhaps the group N-C-S of benzothiazolines is responsible for biological activity¹ and of chelation therapy. Preparation of benzothiazolines by the reactions of aldehyde and ketones with 2-aminothiophenol²⁻⁴ have been reported. They represent a significant class of bidentate and multidentate ligands⁵⁻⁷. The interaction between metal ions and amino acids is of considerable interest as models for metal-protein reactions and models in a variety of biological systems⁸. An intensive number of studies on the formation of mixed ligand complexes reveal a realization of their growing importance, particularly in their role in biological process⁹. The formation of mixed ligand chelates is a general

feature of systems where a metal is present with two or more ligands. The study of these complexes shows that their formations are a favoured process over that of simple complexes¹⁰. The ternary complexes of the Schiff bases and amino acids with metal ions bear the importance of both Schiff bases and amino acids. In addition, these species may be considered as relatively simple models for ternary enzyme/metal ion/inhibitor¹¹. On the other hand Cu^{II} complexes have extensively been studied in recent years. Their flexibility, facility of preparation and capacity of stabilizing unusual oxidation states can explain their successful performance in mimicking peculiar geometries around the metal, leading to very interesting spectroscopic properties and varied reactivities¹²⁻¹⁴. The complexity of the stereochemistry of Cu^{II} complexes is well known¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Owing to the plasticity of the coordination sphere, which is well-known as a feature of copper, Cu^{II} ion forms a variety of complexes with coordination number 4-6¹⁸. The geometries around the central Cu^{II} atom

are controlled primarily by the combinations of various ligands and the steric constraints in the ligand itself. For example, five-coordinate Cu^{II} complexes, in most cases take on many different geometries ranging between square pyramidal (SP) and trigonal bipyramidal (TBP)¹⁹. The stereochemistry of five-coordinated Cu^{II} complexes has been reviewed and discussed comprehensively by Hathaway^{20,21}. Cu^{II} complexes with tridentate^{21–27} and tetradentate²⁸ Schiff base ligands were reported. Copper complexes have been reported to inhibit bacterial, fungal, yeast, algal, mycoplasma, and viral growth, as well as to cause the death of these organisms²⁹. So, the nature of the ligand and metal are of paramount importance in the interaction of the complexes with the DNA molecule, which would help in the design of newer drugs and develop new selective, efficient DNA recognition and cleaving agents. Moreover, Cu^{II} -peptide complexes may be regarded as models for both protein-DNA and antitumor agent-DNA interactions, since peptides are the basic structural units of HSA that recognize a specific base sequence of DNA³⁰. Benzothiazole based copper(II)-di-peptide complexes have the potential to be nucleic acid molecular probes and new therapeutic reagents for treating HepG2³¹. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to assess the pharmacological properties of the benzothiazoline based copper(II) complexes with peptides.

In the present investigation ternary complexes of Cu^{II} with 3-acyl 2-(2'-hydroxy-5-Y phenyl)benzothiazoline, Y = H, Cl, NO_2 , OCH_3 (Fig. 1) as the primary ligand and L-glycine as secondary ligand have been synthesised and further their structure has been described.

Fig. 1

Chemicals :

The chemicals used were of the highest purity accessible. 2-Aminothiophenol from Alfa Aesar Lancaster, 5-Y salicylaldehyde (where Y = H, Cl, NO_2 , OCH_3) from

Sigma Aldrich, copper chloride and L-glycine from SD's fine chemicals. The organic solvents used were obtained as pure grade materials. All the experiments were performed at room temperature.

Instrumentation :

Elemental analysis was carried out on INCA EDX instrument. The IR spectra (KBr) was recorded on a Bruker Optics Tensor-27 FTIR. Molar conductivities of the complexes were measured in DMSO at room temperature using Digison conductivity instrument. The MS data was collected on Agilent Single Quad Mass Spectrometer. Thermal studies were carried out in a dynamic nitrogen atmosphere (20 ml min^{-1}) with a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ using a Shimadzu TGA-50H. UV-Visible measurements were performed using a UV-Vis 2450 Shimadzu spectrophotometer in the range 200–1100 nm. ESR measurements were carried out in air atmosphere at room temperature on Varian E112 type spectrometer using L-band microwave source. The melting points were determined with Polmon apparatus (Model No. MP-90).

Synthesis of the ligand :

By condensation of 2-aminothiophenol with 5-Y salicylaldehyde (where Y = H, Cl, NO_2 and OCH_3) in equimolar ratio in a polar solvent 2-(2'-hydroxy-5-X phenyl)benzothiazoline is formed. Acylation of the 3-amino group was achieved by using acetic anhydride³² yielding 3-acyl 2-(2'-hydroxy-5-Y phenyl)benzothiazoline.

Synthesis of the complexes :

The title compound (0.005 mol) and L-glycine (0.005 mol) mixture were dissolved in warm methanol and water respectively and refluxed for 30 min. Anhydrous CuCl_2 (0.01 mol) dissolved in methanol is added to the above ligands mixture and refluxed on water bath for 8–10 h at 70–80 $^\circ\text{C}$ by adjusting pH in the range 6.0–7.0 to enable complex formation. The precipitated ternary complex was filtered, washed with water, hot ethanol and dried in vacuum at room temperature. The product was dried in air and stored in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 under vacuum.

Results and discussion

The elemental analyses data along with some physical properties of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The non-electrolytic nature of the ternary complexes is evi-

Table 1. Mass spectral data, CHN, molar conductivity and magnetic moment values

No.	Compd.	Molecular formula	Colour	Mass spectral data	Analysis (%) :			Λ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
					Found	Calcd.			
1	Cu-AHPBT-Gly	Cu-C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	Light brown	391	C	H	N	3.2	2.13
					(49.8)	(2.9)	(6.8)		
2	Cu-AHCPBT-Gly	Cu-C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ ClS	Yellowish brown	423	C	H	N	3.1	1.81
					(46)	(2.7)	(6.3)		
3	Cu-AHMPBT-Gly	Cu-C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₅ S	Dark brown	435	C	H	N	3.4	1.60
					(49.2)	(3.4)	(6.4)		
4	Cu-AHNPBT-Gly	Cu-C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₆ S	Brown	432	C	H	N	3.5	1.63
					(44.9)	(2.64)	(9.2)		

dent from the molar conductivities measured in DMSO (Table 1).

Infrared spectra and mode of bonding :

IR spectrum of the complexes shows split bands at 3230–3326 cm^{-1} due to the presence of NH_2 group. The C=O stretching vibration is also shifted to the lower frequencies. The bands in the regions 1594–1586 and 1412–

1408 cm^{-1} , due to ν_{asym} (COO^-) and ν_{sym} (COO^-) of the amino acids, appear in the complexes at 1552–1543 and 1316–1306 cm^{-1} . The shift of these two bands suggests the involvement of the carboxylic groups of the amino acids in complex formation^{33,34}. Hence, the amino acid moiety is chelated to the metal ion through five-member ring. The Cu-O and Cu-N vibrations^{35,36} in the spectra of

Fig. 2. IR spectrum of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

Fig. 3. IR spectrum of Cu-AHCPBT-Gly.

Fig. 4. IR spectrum of Cu-AHMPBT-Gly.

Fig. 5. IR spectrum of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

complexes (Figs. 2-5) is confirmed by the newly formed bands at $\sim 524\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the metal-ligand bonding. The comparative IR spectral data of AHPBT, AHCPBT, AHMPBT and AHPBT and their Cu^{II} ternary complexes are presented in Table 2.

Magnetic and UV-Vis measurements :

The values of magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) are found to be in the range 1.6–2.3 B.M. (Table 1). The electronic spec-

tra of Cu^{II} ternary complexes are compared with those of the free ligands in uncoordinated form (Figs. 6-9). Two bands appeared at 259–251 nm ($38610\text{--}39840\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 348–328 nm ($28735\text{--}30487\text{ cm}^{-1}$) can be assigned to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ and $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions in respective systems.

Table 2. IR bands and their assignments for 3-acyl 2-(2'-hydroxy-5-X phenyl)benzothiazoline (**1a-d**) and its Cu ternary complexes (**1**)-(4)

No.	Compd.	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-X}}$	ν_{NH_2}	$\nu_{\text{Cu-O/Cu-N}}$
1a	AHPBT	1635	–	3211	–
1	Cu-AHPBT-Gly	1608	–	3312	522/472
1b	AHCPBT	1620	740	3165	–
2	Cu-AHCPBT-Gly	1604	742	3360	524/450
1c	AHMPBT	1631	1423	3226	–
3	Cu-AHMPBT-Gly	1591	1453	3321	509/470
1d	AHPBT	1689	1334	3130	–
4	Cu-AHPBT-Gly	1602	1328	3332	531/462

Fig. 6. UV spectrum of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

Fig. 7. UV spectrum of Cu-AHCPBT-Gly.

Fig. 9. UV spectrum of Cu-AHNPBT-Gly.

Fig. 8. UV spectrum of Cu-AHMPBT-Gly.

The electronic spectra of complexes showed low energy band at 958–609 nm ($10437\text{--}16420\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and strong high energy bands at 429–353 nm ($23310\text{--}28328\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The low energy band in the position may be assigned to the transitions $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{yz}$; d_{z^2} ; d_{xy} ^{37,38}. The strong high energy band admixed with ligand chromophore peaks is attributable to charge transfer transitions.

Mass spectra :

The mass spectra of the Cu^{II} metal complexes show m/z peaks which are in accordance with the expected mass and the corresponding analysed data are presented in Figs. 10-13 and Table 1. The data and the mass spectra confirm

that metal complexes are formed in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio.

EDS analysis :

Electron Dispersive Spectroscopy gives the elemental composition of the samples. The elemental composition of the ternary complexes from EDS (Figs. 14-17) is in concurrence with the calculated values except for hydrogen which is evident from the CHN analysis of Cu^{II} ternary complexes (Table 1). The weight % of Cu^{II} is also in close agreement with the calculated values. The absence of chlorine is also evident from these spectra except for Cu-AHCPBT-Gly where in chlorine is present in the ligand. The mass data supports for the same.

The ESR spectra of copper complexes provide information of importance in studying the metal ion environment and also metal ligand bond covalency. The L band ESR spectra recorded at RT for the Cu^{II} ternary complexes in the present investigation are given in Figs. 18-21. In all copper complexes under study the g value is nearly anisotropic. The average value of g_{\perp} and g_{\parallel} in each complex is presented below (Table 3). Even though hyperfine interactions are evident from ESR spectrum of Cu-AHPBT-Gly, because of poor resolution it is less informative to understand the delocalisation of unpaired electron on to ligand moiety.

Thermo gravimetric analysis of Cu-AHPBT, Cu-AHCPBT, Cu-AHMPBT and Cu-AHNPBT :

Cu^{II} ternary complexes (Figs. 22-25) exhibited weight

Fig. 10. Mass spectrum of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

loss in the range of 150–200 °C, indicating the loss of occluded water in the TGA curve. The decomposition of the benzothiazoline ligand is indicated by the loss of weight in steps from 200 to 300 °C. Above 400 °C corresponds to the partial decomposition of the complex. The percentage of final residue remaining above 900 °C indicates the formation of thermally stable residue.

A review of literature reveals that aryl benzothiazolines when interact with metal ions to form solid complexes, various structural changes occur in ligands^{39–42}. The studies on 2-(2'-hydroxy)-phenyl benzothiazoline complexes earlier reported revealed that in presence of Cu^{II} metal ion the cleavage of thiazoline ring, subsequent Schiff base formation through the transfer of proton from nitrogen to

sulphur and then dissociation of same proton from sulphur and second proton from hydroxyl group of phenyl ring occurred enabling its copper complex formation⁴³. In present study, on contrary, the ring cleavage is hindered by acetyl group at ring nitrogen in presence of metal ions under the conditions of metal complex formation. Only hydroxyl proton dissociation occurs during formation of complex and the benzothiazoline ring remain as such.

As a general conclusion it can be revealed that the benzothiazoline ligand is coordinated to the metal centre via the N of thiazoline ring and O of phenyl ring upon deprotonation of the H from O-H leading to the possible formation of 6-membered ring and glycine is bonded to

Fig. 11. Mass spectrum of Cu-AHCPBT-Gly.

the metal through the nitrogen of amine and oxygen of carboxylate group (Fig. 26).

Biological studies :

Antibacterial and antifungal activity :

The antimicrobial activity for the title compounds and its Cu^{II} ternary complexes was tested *in vitro* against five standard bacterial strains (*E. coli*, *S. marcescens*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*) and one fungal strain (*Candida albican*).

The antimicrobial assay was performed using the disk

diffusion method⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. A loop full of microorganism was inoculated in 10 ml nutrient medium (NM) and incubated for 12-16 h at 37 ± 1 °C. Later, 200 μ L of the overnight culture was transferred into fresh 10 ml NM and grown up to mid logarithm phase ($0.4-0.5_{620}$). The microorganisms were then washed twice with sterile saline pH 7.4 and resuspended in 1 ml of PBS (phosphate buffer saline) to concentration of $1-2 \times 10^9$ CFU/ml. Subsequently, bacterial load ($1-2 \times 10^7$ CFU) was added to 5 ml agar NM and spread in a petriplate. In order to add the antimicrobial compound, a circular hole was punched in the

Fig. 12. Mass spectrum of Cu-AHMPBT-Gly.

agar plate. After that, the 10 μL of antimicrobial test compound was placed into the well and plates were incubated for 24 h at 37 ± 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in inverted position. The inhibition zones around each disc was measured by using Hiantibiotic zone scaleTM (Himedia, India) in mm and compared with the controls after 24 h zone of incubation. Ampicillin was used as a standard drug for antibacterial activity and *Candida* was used as a standard drug for antifungal activity.

AHCPBT, AHNBPBT and their copper complexes when screened against bacteria and fungus, showed varying activities (Table 4). The ligands showed prominent antibac-

terial activity except that these are inactive with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The antifungal activity of AHCPBT and AHNBPBT is almost comparable with that of *Candida* standard. Among the title compounds, the AHNBPBT showed pronounced antimicrobial and antifungal activity. The Cu^{II} ternary complex of AHCPBT and AHNBPBT showed activity against one Gram-negative and Gram-positive microorganism mentioned above, whereas they showed no activity against fungus. It can be inferred that the antimicrobial activity has profoundly decreased in the ternary complexes when compared to the Cu^{II} binary complexes (Cu-AHCPBT and Cu-AHNBPBT)⁴⁷.

Fig. 13. Mass spectrum of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

Fig. 14. EDX image of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

Fig. 15. EDX image of Cu-AHCPBT-Gly.

Fig. 16. EDX image of Cu-AHMPBT-Gly.

Fig. 17. EDX image of Cu-AHNPBT-Gly.

Fig. 18. ESR spectra of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

Table 3. *g* values of Cu^{II} ternary complexes

Complex	' <i>g</i> ' factor
Cu-AHPBT-Gly	2.0438
Cu-AHCPBT-Gly	2.0232
Cu-AHNPBT-Gly	2.0438
Cu-AHMPBT-Gly	2.0232

DNA cleavage studies :

Gel electrophoresis is a widely used technique for the analysis of nucleic acids and proteins. Electrophoresis is a method of separating substances based on the rate of movement while under the influence of an electric field. Agarose gel electrophoresis is used for the DNA cleavage stud-

Fig. 19. ESR spectra of Cu-AHCPBT-Gly.

Fig. 20. ESR spectra of Cu-AHMPBT-Gly.

Fig. 21. ESR spectrum of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

Fig. 22. TGA curve of Cu-AHPBT-Gly.

Fig. 23. TGA curve of Cu-AHCPBT-Gly.

Fig. 24. TGA curve of Cu-AHMPBT-Gly.

ies. Agarose gel electrophoresis is a successful method to cleave super coiled DNA in to Nicked Circular and linear DNA forms. For the hydrolytic cleavage of DNA, super coiled (SC) plasmid DNA is a central substrate. For the DNA cleavage analysis a potency of compounds are quan-

titatively evaluated on super coiled plasmid PBR322 in the absence of oxidizing or reducing agents.

The ligands AHPBT, AHCPBT, AHNPBT and their Cu^{II} ternary complexes have been tested for DNA cleavage studies. The results revealed that only Cu^{II} -AHCPBT-

Fig. 25. TGA curve of Cu-AHNPBT-Gly.

Fig. 26

Gly and Cu^{II}-AHNPBT-Gly are efficient DNA cleavers as they have converted super coiled DNA (form I) into relaxed DNA (form II) (Fig. 27). On contrary among the Cu^{II} binary complexes Cu^{II}-AHNPBT converted super coiled DNA (form I) not only into relaxed DNA (form II) but also resulted in linear DNA (form III) indicating that binary complex is more efficient in cleaving DNA than corresponding ternary complex wherein conversion to only relaxed DNA (form II) is observed.

Table 4. Antimicrobial activity of the ligands and their Cu-complexes

Sample	Description	Bacteria					Fungus
		Gram-negative type			Gram-positive type		
		<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	
AHCPBT	Test sample	7.00	8.00	0.00	0.00	8.50	5.5
AHNPBT	Test sample	14.50	16.50	0.00	15.00	15.50	17.5
Cu-AHCPBT	Test sample	7.00	9.50	0.00	8.00	9.50	2
Cu-AHNPBT	Test sample	7.50	8.00	5.50	9.00	9.00	3
Cu-AHCPBT-Gly	Test sample	0.00	9.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.00
Cu-AHNPBT-Gly	Test sample	0.00	5.50	0.00	0.00	7.50	0.00
Ampicillin	Standard	15.50	16.00	4.50	8.00	18.00	0.00
Candida	Standard	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7

Fig. 27. DNA cleavage activity of ligands and its Cu^{II} ternary complexes : Lane 1 : DNA marker (1 μ L + 4 μ L Tris-HCl buffer). Lane 2 : DNA (1 μ L + 4 μ L Tris-HCl buffer) + AHPBT (5 μ L of 2 mg/ml). Lane 3 : DNA (1 μ L + 4 μ L Tris-HCl buffer) + Cu^{II}-AHPBT-Gly (5 μ L of 2 mg/ml). Lane 4 : DNA (1 μ L + 4 μ L Tris-HCl buffer) + AHCPBT (5 μ L of 2 mg/ml). Lane 5 : DNA (1 μ L + 4 μ L Tris-HCl buffer) + Cu^{II}-AHCPBT-Gly (5 μ L of 2 mg/ml). Lane 6 : DNA (1 μ L + 4 μ L Tris-HCl buffer) + AHNPBT (5 μ L of 2 mg/ml). Lane 7 : DNA (1 μ L + 4 μ L Tris-HCl buffer) + Cu^{II}-AHNPBT-Gly (5 μ L of 2 mg/ml).

Conclusion

In the present study Cu^{II}-ternary complexes were synthesized, characterized and structurally elucidated by various spectro-analytical techniques. The Cu^{II}-ternary complexes of AHCPBT and AHNPBT showed antibacterial activity. The DNA cleavage studies inferred that Cu^{II}-AHCPBT-Gly and Cu^{II}-AHNPBT-Gly are more effective in the cleavage of plasmid PBR-322 DNA.

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